

Deliverable 2

D2: 'Guidelines for the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in the microfluidics industry supply chain'

Work package 1

Organisation Name of Lead Partner for D2: INESC MN

Submission Date: 30 of May 2024

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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This report was written as part of activity 1.3.6 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

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1. Scope

This report addresses the activity A1.3.2 defined in the JRP protocol as:

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.3.6 M33	<p>Using input from A1.3.1 - A1.3.5, INESC MN with support from CETIAT, IPQ, DTI, UofG, HSG-IMIT, TUBITAK, EnablingMNT and CMI will develop guidelines for the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics. These will be shared with the relevant standardisation group such as CEN/TC332/WG7 and/or ISO/TC48/WG3.</p> <p>Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator on behalf of INESC MN, CETIAT, IPQ, DTI, UofG, CMI, HSG-IMIT, EnablingMNT and TUBITAK will submit the guidelines to EURAMET as D2: 'Guidelines for the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in the microfluidics industry supply chain'.</p>	INESC MN , CETIAT, IPQ, DTI, UofG, CMI, HSG-IMIT, TUBITAK, EnablingMNT

2. Purpose

With this document we intend to establish a standardized approach for implementing consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics, ensuring efficient and reliable control of fluid flow in microfluidic devices. The guidelines apply to the design and implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidic devices, including lab-on-a-chip (LOC) devices, micro-total analysis systems (μ TAS), and other microfluidic platforms.

3. Key Requirements:

Key requirements identified are as follows:

- **Consensus algorithm**¹: Implement a consensus algorithm that ensures agreement among multiple sensors or actuators in the microfluidic device.
- **Flow control protocol**: Define a standardized flow control protocol that integrates with the consensus algorithm to regulate fluid flow.
- **Sensor integration**: Ensure seamless integration of sensors and actuators in the microfluidic device to enable accurate and reliable flow control.
- **Communication protocol**: Establish a communication protocol to facilitate data exchange between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm.
- **Testing and validation**: Perform thorough testing and validation of the consensus-based flow control specifications to ensure reliable operation and optimal performance.

¹ A consensus algorithm is a protocol that ensures that multiple sensors or actuators in the microfluidic device agree on a single value or action, such as a measurement or control signal, despite the potential for individual errors or malfunctions in the devices.

4. Implementation Guidelines:

After discussion within the Partners of the Project consortium, from input gathered in Surveys [1-4] and Workshops on Standardization for Microfluidics [5-7] organized by the project, this document gathers five implementation guidelines presented below:

- **Guideline A:** Design a consensus-based flow control system that incorporates multiple sensors and actuators.
- **Guideline B:** Implement a standardized flow control protocol that integrates with the consensus algorithm.
- **Guideline C:** Integrate sensors and actuators in the microfluidic device to ensure accurate and reliable flow control.
- **Guideline D:** Establish a communication protocol to facilitate data exchange between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm.
- **Guideline E:** Test and validate the consensus-based flow control specifications to ensure reliable operation and optimal performance.

By following these guidelines, designers and manufacturers of microfluidic devices have additional tools to ensure efficient and reliable flow control in their devices, enabling accurate and precise use.

5. Existing operational protocols applicable for flow control in microfluidics

Operational protocols applicable for flow control in microfluidics were identified in activity A1.2.3. They are based on documents found in web sites of ISO, ASTM, CEN and Nature Protocols and from the EMPIR project 18HLT08 MeDD II - Metrology for Drug Delivery [8]. They can be used to support the implementation of the guidelines identified above. The list below presents the more relevant documents used in flow control specifications in the microfluidics industry supply chain.

Infusion devices, syringe pumps, medical applications

- IEC 60601-2-24 Medical electrical equipment – Part 2-24: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and controllers
- AAMI TIR101:2021, Fluid delivery performance testing for infusion pumps
- IPQ, Metrology in Health – Good Practice Guide, Part II, Chapter III – Infusion Pumps, 2018
- ISO 28620:2020 Medical devices — Non-electrically driven portable infusion devices
- ISO 7886-2:2020, Sterile hypodermic syringes for single use — Part 2: Syringes for use with power-driven syringe pumps

Oil industry

- ASTM D7996-15 Standard Test Method for Measuring Visible Spectrum of Asphaltenes in Heavy Fuel Oils and Crude Oils by Spectroscopy in a Microfluidic Platform

Biology and chemistry

- Prabhu, G.R.D., Yang, TH., Hsu, CY. et al., Facilitating chemical and biochemical experiments with electronic microcontrollers and single-board computers, *Nature Protocols* 15, 925–990 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-019-0272-1>
- Huh, D., Kim, H., Fraser, J. et al., Microfabrication of human organs-on-chips, *Nature Protocols* 8, 2135–2157 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2013.137>.

6. Guideline A: How to design a consensus-based flow control system that incorporates multiple sensors and actuators?

A possible path to design a consensus-based flow control system that incorporates multiple sensors and actuators is described below:

Step 1: Define the System Requirements

- Identify the type of microfluidic device being designed (e.g., lab-on-a-chip, micro-total analysis system, etc.).
- Determine the fluid flow control requirements (e.g., flow rate, pressure, temperature, etc.).
- Identify the sensors and actuators needed for flow control (e.g., pressure sensors, flow sensors, pumps, valves, etc.).
- Define the communication protocol and data exchange requirements between sensors and actuators.

Step 2: Design the Sensor Network

- Choose the type of sensors needed for each flow control parameter (e.g., pressure sensor for pressure control, flow sensor for flow rate control, etc.).
- Determine the sensor location within the complete microfluidic system and number of sensors required for each parameter.
- Design the sensor network architecture to ensure reliable and accurate data collection.
- Ensure that each sensor can transmit data to the consensus algorithm.

Step 3: Design the Actuator Network

- Choose the type of actuators needed for each flow control parameter (e.g., pump for flow rate control, valve for pressure control, etc.).
- Determine the actuator location within the complete microfluidic system and number of actuators required for each parameter.
- Design the actuator network architecture to ensure reliable and accurate control of fluid flow.
- Ensure that each actuator can receive control signals from the consensus algorithm.

Step 4: Design the Consensus Algorithm

- Choose a consensus algorithm that can be used in a distributed system (e.g., majority vote, weighted average, etc.).
- Determine the communication protocol and data exchange requirements between sensors and actuators.
- Design the consensus algorithm to ensure reliable and accurate decision-making.
- Ensure that the consensus algorithm can integrate with the sensor and actuator networks.

Step 5: Design the Flow Control Protocol

- Choose a standardized flow control protocol that integrates with the consensus algorithm.
- Determine the flow control parameters (e.g., flow rate, pressure, temperature, etc.) to be controlled.
- Design the flow control protocol to ensure reliable and accurate control of fluid flow.
- Ensure that the flow control protocol can integrate with the sensor and actuator networks.

Step 6: Integrate Sensors, Actuators, and Consensus Algorithm

- Connect sensors to the consensus algorithm to transmit data.
- Connect actuators to the consensus algorithm to receive control signals.
- Ensure that data is transmitted and received correctly between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm.
- Test the system to ensure that it functions as intended.

Step 7: Test and Validate the System

- Perform thorough testing of the system to ensure reliable and accurate operation.
- Validate the system by comparing its performance with theoretical models, simulation results or reference system(s) performances (such as calibrated sensors, transfer standards, etc.).
- Conduct thorough debugging to identify and fix any errors or issues.
- Ensure that the system meets all functional and performance requirements.

7. Guideline B: How to implement a standardized flow control protocol that integrates with the consensus algorithm?

Step 1: Define the Flow Control Parameters

- Identify the flow control parameters that need to be controlled (e.g., flow rate, pressure, temperature, etc.).
- Determine the range of values for each parameter that needs to be controlled (e.g., flow rate: (0-100) $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, pressure: (0-10) kPa, etc.).
- Define the units of measurement for each parameter (e.g., $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, kPa, $^{\circ}\text{C}$, etc.).

Step 2: Choose a Standardized Flow Control Protocol

- Research existing standardized flow control protocols (e.g., those identified in section 5, etc.).
- Choose a protocol that is widely accepted and compatible with the consensus algorithm.
- Consider the complexity and scalability of the protocol when making your decision.

Step 3: Design the Flow Control Protocol

- Define the protocol's architecture and structure (e.g., client-server, peer-to-peer, etc.).
- Determine the communication protocol and data exchange requirements between sensors and actuators.
- Design the protocol's message structure and data formats.
- Define the protocol's error handling and fault tolerance mechanisms.

Step 4: Implement the Flow Control Protocol

- Use a programming language (e.g., Python, C++, Java, etc.) to implement the protocol.
- Use a library or framework (e.g., Twisted, Boost.Asio, etc.) to simplify the implementation.
- Implement the protocol's message structure and data formats.
- Test the protocol to ensure it functions correctly.

Step 5: Integrate the Flow Control Protocol with the Consensus Algorithm

- Use a programming language (e.g., Python, C++, Java, etc.) to integrate the flow control protocol with the consensus algorithm.
- Use a library or framework (e.g., Twisted, Boost.Asio, etc.) to simplify the integration.
- Ensure that data is transmitted and received correctly between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm.
- Test the system to ensure it functions correctly.

Step 6: Test and Validate the System

- Perform thorough testing of the system to ensure reliable and accurate operation.
- Validate the system by comparing its performance with theoretical models, simulation results or reference system(s) performances (such as calibrated sensors, transfer standards, etc.).
- Conduct thorough debugging to identify and fix any errors or issues.
- Ensure that the system meets all functional and performance requirements.

Step 7: Document the Flow Control Protocol

- Write documentation that describes the flow control protocol's architecture, structure, and implementation.

- Document the protocol's message structure and data formats.
- Document the protocol's error handling and fault tolerance mechanisms.
- Provide examples of how to use the protocol.

Example of a standardized flow control protocol:

- SCL (Serial Communication Language): a standardized protocol for communicating with microfluidic devices using a serial interface.
- SCPI (Standard Commands for Programmable Instruments): a standardized protocol for communicating with microfluidic devices using a command-line interface.

Example of a flow control protocol implementation:

- Using Python with Twisted library to implement a SCL-based flow control protocol.
- Using C++ with Boost.Asio library to implement a SCPI-based flow control protocol.

Note: The above example is for illustration purposes only and may not be actual implementation examples.

8. Guideline C: How to integrate sensors and actuators in the microfluidic device to ensure accurate and reliable flow control?

Step 1: Choose the Right Sensors and Actuators

- Identify the type of sensors and actuators needed for flow control (e.g., pressure sensors, flow sensors, pumps, valves, etc.).
- Consider the specific requirements of the microfluidic device, such as the type of fluid being used, the desired flow rate, and the required pressure.
- Select sensors and actuators that are compatible with the microfluidic device's materials and operating conditions.

Step 2: Design the Sensor Placement

- Determine the optimal placement of sensors within the microfluidic device to ensure accurate measurement of flow parameters.
- Consider factors such as fluid flow direction, pressure drop, and temperature gradients when designing the sensor placement.
- Ensure that sensors are easily accessible for maintenance and replacement.

Step 3: Integrate Sensors with Microfluidic Device

- Connect sensors to the microfluidic device using suitable connectors or interfaces (e.g., electrical connections, fluidic connections).
- Ensure that sensors are securely attached to the microfluidic device to prevent damage or disconnection.
- Test the sensors to ensure they are functioning correctly and providing accurate data.

Step 4: Design the Actuator Placement

- Determine the optimal placement of actuators within the microfluidic device to control flow parameters.
- Consider factors such as fluid flow direction, pressure drop, and temperature gradients when designing the actuator placement.
- Ensure that actuators are easily accessible for maintenance and replacement.

Step 5: Integrate Actuators with Microfluidic Device

- Connect actuators to the microfluidic device using suitable connectors or interfaces (e.g., electrical connections, fluidic connections).
- Ensure that actuators are securely attached to the microfluidic device to prevent damage or disconnection.
- Test the actuators to ensure they are functioning correctly and providing accurate control.

Step 6: Implement Sensor-Actuator Integration

- Use a programming language (e.g., Python, C++, Java, etc.) to implement the integration of sensors and actuators.
- Use a library or framework (e.g., Twisted, Boost, Asio, etc.) to simplify the integration.
- Ensure that sensor data is transmitted correctly to the actuators to control flow parameters.
- Test the system to ensure it functions correctly.

Step 7: Test and Validate the System

- Perform thorough testing of the system to ensure accurate and reliable flow control.
- Validate the system by comparing its performance with theoretical models, simulation results or reference system(s) performances (such as calibrated sensors, transfer standards, etc.).
- Conduct thorough debugging to identify and fix any errors or issues.
- Ensure that the system meets all functional and performance requirements.

Example of sensor-actuator integration:

- Using a pressure sensor to monitor fluid pressure and a valve actuator to control fluid flow rate.
- Using a flow sensor to monitor fluid flow rate and a pump actuator to control fluid pressure.

Note: The above example is for illustration purposes only and may not be actual implementation examples.

9. Guideline D: How to establish a communication protocol to facilitate data exchange between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm?

Step 1: Define the Communication Requirements

- Determine the type of data that needs to be exchanged between sensors, actuators, and the consensus algorithm (e.g., sensor readings, actuator commands, etc.).
- Identify the frequency and volume of data exchange required.
- Consider the latency and reliability requirements of the communication protocol.

Step 2: Choose a Communication Protocol

- Research existing communication protocols (e.g., TCP/IP, UDP, MQTT, etc.).
- Choose a protocol that is widely accepted and compatible with the sensors, actuators, and consensus algorithm.
- Consider the complexity and scalability of the protocol when making your decision.

Step 3: Design the Communication Protocol

- Define the protocol's architecture and structure (e.g., client-server, peer-to-peer, etc.).
- Determine the data formats and message structures used for data exchange.
- Design the protocol's error handling and fault tolerance mechanisms.
- Consider security and encryption requirements for data transmission.

Step 4: Implement the Communication Protocol

- Use a programming language (e.g., Python, C++, Java, etc.) to implement the protocol.
- Use a library or framework (e.g., Twisted, Boost.Asio, etc.) to simplify the implementation.
- Implement the protocol's message structure and data formats.
- Test the protocol to ensure it functions correctly.

Step 5: Integrate Sensors and Actuators with the Communication Protocol

- Connect sensors and actuators to the communication protocol using suitable interfaces (e.g., electrical connections, serial connections).
- Ensure that sensors and actuators are properly configured to communicate with the protocol.

- Test the sensors and actuators to ensure they are functioning correctly and transmitting data correctly.

Step 6: Integrate Consensus Algorithm with the Communication Protocol

- Connect the consensus algorithm to the communication protocol using a suitable interface (e.g., serial connection, network connection).
- Ensure that the consensus algorithm is properly configured to communicate with the protocol.
- Test the consensus algorithm to ensure it is functioning correctly and receiving data correctly.

Step 7: Test and Validate the System

- Perform thorough testing of the system to ensure accurate and reliable data exchange.
- Validate the system by comparing its performance with theoretical models, simulation results or reference system(s) performances (such as calibrated sensors, transfer standards, etc.).
- Conduct thorough debugging to identify and fix any errors or issues.
- Ensure that the system meets all functional and performance requirements.

Example of communication protocol:

- Using MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) protocol for data exchange between sensors, actuators, and consensus algorithm.
- Using TCP/IP (Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol) protocol for data exchange between sensors, actuators, and consensus algorithm.

Note: The above example is for illustration purposes only and may not be actual implementation examples.

10. Guideline E: How to test and validate the consensus-based flow control specifications to ensure reliable operation and optimal performance?

Step 1: Identify Test Scenarios

- Identify the key scenarios that will be tested, such as:
 - Normal operation: Flow control in normal conditions with no errors or faults.
 - Error handling: Flow control in the presence of errors or faults, such as sensor failures or communication losses.
 - Boundary conditions: Flow control at extreme conditions, such as very low or high flow rates.
- Determine the specific test scenarios and conditions that will be used.

Step 2: Develop Test Plans

- Develop a detailed test plan for each test scenario, including:
 - Test objectives: Clearly define the objectives of the test.
 - Test steps: Outline the specific steps to be performed during the test.
 - Test metrics: Identify the metrics to be used to measure the performance of the system.
- Ensure that the test plans are comprehensive and cover all possible scenarios.

Step 3: Conduct Testing

- Conduct the testing according to the developed test plans.
- Use a combination of automated testing and manual testing to ensure thorough coverage.
- Use simulation tools or hardware-in-the-loop testing to simulate real-world scenarios.

Step 4: Analyze Results

- Analyze the results of each test scenario to determine whether the system meets the specified requirements.
- Use statistical analysis and data visualization techniques to identify trends and patterns in the data.
- Compare results with expected performance metrics to ensure compliance with specifications.

Step 5: Validate Consensus Algorithm

- Validate the consensus algorithm by simulating different scenarios and analyzing the results.
- Use statistical analysis and data visualization techniques to identify trends and patterns in the data.
- Compare results with expected performance metrics to ensure compliance with specifications.

Step 6: Validate Sensor-Actuator Integration

- Validate the integration of sensors and actuators by simulating different scenarios and analyzing the results.
- Use statistical analysis and data visualization techniques to identify trends and patterns in the data.
- Compare results with expected performance metrics to ensure compliance with specifications.

Step 7: Conduct System-Level Testing

- Conduct system-level testing to ensure that all components work together seamlessly.

- Use a combination of automated testing and manual testing to ensure thorough coverage.
- Use simulation tools or hardware-in-the-loop testing to simulate real-world scenarios.

Step 8: Validate Performance Metrics

- Validate performance metrics such as flow rate, pressure, and temperature using data from sensors and actuators.
- Use statistical analysis and data visualization techniques to identify trends and patterns in the data.
- Compare results with expected performance metrics to ensure compliance with specifications.

Step 9: Identify and Fix Issues

- Identify any issues or defects found during testing and debugging.
- Fix issues by modifying code, updating firmware, or replacing hardware components.
- Re-run tests to ensure that issues are resolved.

Step 10: Document Results

- Document the results of each test scenario, including any issues or defects found.
- Document any modifications made during testing and debugging.
- Document any lessons learned during testing and validation.

Example of testing:

1. Testing the consensus algorithm by simulating different scenarios, such as:
 - Normal operation: Simulating a normal flow rate with no errors or faults.
 - Error handling: Simulating a flow rate with an error, such as a sensor failure.
 - Boundary conditions: Simulating a flow rate at extreme conditions, such as very low or high flow rates.
2. Testing the sensor-actuator integration by simulating different scenarios, such as:
 - Normal operation: Simulating a normal flow rate with no errors or faults.
 - Error handling: Simulating a flow rate with an error, such as a sensor failure or actuator malfunction.
3. Testing the system-level integration by simulating different scenarios, such as:
 - Normal operation: Simulating a normal flow rate with no errors or faults.
 - Error handling: Simulating a flow rate with an error, such as a sensor failure or actuator malfunction.

Note: The above example is for illustration purposes only and may not be actual implementation examples.

Summary

The increasing complexity of microfluidic systems has led to the need for consensus-based flow control specifications to ensure reliable and optimal operation. However, the implementation of these specifications requires careful consideration of various factors, including system architecture, sensor and actuator selection, and control algorithms. Without clear guidelines, the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics may lead to inconsistent results, reduced reliability, and increased risk of errors.

Key Issues

- Lack of Standardization: The lack of standardized guidelines for implementing consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics can lead to inconsistent results and reduced reliability.
- Complexity: The complexity of microfluidic systems requires careful consideration of various factors, including system architecture, sensor and actuator selection, and control algorithms.
- Error Risk: The risk of errors during implementation can be significant if proper guidelines are not followed.
- Scalability: As microfluidic systems become more complex and scalable, the need for consensus-based flow control specifications becomes more critical.

Benefits of Guidelines

- Improved Reliability: Clear guidelines can ensure that consensus-based flow control specifications are implemented consistently and reliably.
- Increased Efficiency: Guidelines can help reduce errors and improve the efficiency of the implementation process.
- Improved Scalability: Guidelines can ensure that consensus-based flow control specifications are scalable and can be applied to complex microfluidic systems.
- Reduced Error Risk: Guidelines can help reduce the risk of errors during implementation.

Conclusion

The need for guidelines for the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics is critical to ensure reliable and optimal operation of these systems. By providing clear guidelines, we can ensure consistency, reliability, and efficiency in the implementation of consensus-based flow control specifications in microfluidics.

References

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- [2] H. van Heeren, [Results survey on microfluidics flow control](#) (November 2015)

[3] H. van Heeren, [Reliability of Microfluidics based Devices and Components](#) – enablingMNT (March 2015)

[4] H. van Heeren, [Microfluidic Interconnections and Chips](#) – enablingMNT (September 2014)

[5] <https://drugmetrology.com>

And MFMET Reports

- A1.1.1 Literature and market research: definitions, characteristics, specifications, application and function of flow control components. [Link](#)
- A1.1.2 Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control. [Link](#)
- A1.1.3 Using the Database/inventory for flow control components. [Link](#), [Link](#)
- A1.1.4 Generic specification list for comparison of flow control components. [Link](#)
- A1.1.5 Communication report on the definition of flow control concepts, terms and components used in microfluidics and related database. [Link](#)
- A1.2.3 Documented example of the test protocol for leakage and burst pressure. [Link](#)
- A1.3.1 Investigation on the State-of-the-art of available methodologies for flow control (nano/micro/meso/macro fluidics). [Link](#)
- A1.3.2 Existing operational conditions and existing operation protocols for flow control. [Link](#)
- A1.3.5 Gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies. [Link](#)

- A2.1.1 Metrology Methodology. [Link](#)
- A2.2.1 Literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the flow properties and microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A2.2.2 Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A2.2.3 Documented example of the test protocol for hydrodynamic resistance, flow rate and volume. [Link](#)
- A2.3.1 Literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the liquid properties and microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A2.3.2 Test protocols for liquid properties related to microfluidic devices. [Link](#)
- A3.2.5. Documented example of wettability test protocol. [Link](#)
- A3.2.7 Documented example of surface roughness measurements. [Link](#)
- A3.3.4 Report on the geometry and dimension of microfluidic component ports. [Link](#)
- A4.1.4 Current state of the art of modularity and heterogenous integration of microfluidic systems. [Link](#)